

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part I

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Six new dyes have been prepared by condensation of 5-iodothioindoxyl with acenaphthenequinone and its derivatives and two more by condensing 5-iodo-isatin with 4-chlorothioindoxyl and 5-iodothioindoxyl respectively. The dyeing properties of the compounds have been studied. The absorption maxima of these and twelve other vat dyes (reported elsewhere) have been recorded.

An attempt has been made to study the shifts in the absorption maxima in the light of the molecular structure of the dyes.

The absorption maxima of fourteen vat dyes were determined on a Beckman DU model spectrophotometer with a view to studying the effect on absorption of substituents in the isatin and thioindoxyl parts of the thioindigoid dye molecule.

In earlier communications¹, the preparation and properties of twelve of these dyes were reported. Two other dyes, 3-(5-iodo)indole-2'-(4'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigo and 3-(5-iodo)indole-2'-(5'-iodo)thionaphthene-indigo have now been prepared and their properties examined.

Extending the investigation, with a view to determining the influence of an iodine atom, when present in the 5-position of a thionaphthene ring of the 2-thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo and its derivatives, six new dyes, represented by the general formula (I), have been synthesised by condensation of 5-iodothioindoxyl² with acenaphthenequinone, 3'-chloro-, 3'-bromo-, 1'-methoxy-, 3'- or 4'-nitro- and 3',4'-dinitro-acenaphthenequinones respectively.

The absorption maxima of these dyes have been determined in pyridine solution on a Beckman DU model spectrophotometer and recorded in Table I.

Substitution of chloro, bromo, and iodo group at the 5-position of the isatin nucleus led to a bathochromic shift, though the shift was very small, ranging from 5 Å to 30 Å. The dibromo and dinitro derivatives, as expected, led to a conspicuous shift towards the

1. Sinha, *this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 463; Guha *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1955, **32**, 777.
2. Sinha, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1956, Part III, 216.

red. Substitution of chlorine and iodine atom at the 5'-position of thioindoxyl nucleus of the dye led to the expected bathochromic shift, the shifts being more pronounced than those when the identical substitutions were effected in isatin nucleus of the dye molecule.

TABLE I

Dye.	$\lambda_{\max}$ (pyridine).	Log ϵ .
1. 3-I-2'-(5'-iodo)B	5175 Å	3.904
2. 3-(5-Chloro) I-2'-(5'-iodo)B	5180	3.360
3. 3-(5-Bromo) I-2'-(5'-iodo)B	5190	3.408
4. 3-(5-iodo) I-2'-(5'-iodo) B	5220	4.000
5. 3-(5,7-Dibromo) I-2' (5'-iodo)B	5210	3.799
6. 3-(5-Bromo- 7-nitro) I-2'-(5'-iodo)B	5290	3.600
7. 3-(5,7-Dinitro) I-2'(5-iodo) B	5280	3.910
8. 3-I-2'-(4'-chloro)B	5040	4.131
9. 3-(5-Chloro) I-2'-(4'-chloro)B	5040	4.107
10. 3-(5-Bromo) I-2'-(4'-chloro)B	5050	3.863
11. 3-(5-Iodo) I-2'-(4'-chloro)B	5055	4.095
12. 3-(5,7-Dibromo) I-2'-(4'-chloro)B	5070	3.339
13. 3-(5-Bromo- 7-nitro) I-2'-(4'-chloro)B	5140	4.896
14. 3-(5,7-Dinitro) I-2'-(4'-chloro)B	5175	3.993
15. 2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-AI	5275	4.259
16. 2-(5-Iodo) T-8-(3'-chloro)AI	5280	4.360
17. 2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-bromo)AI	5280	4.116
18. 2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(1'-methoxy)AI	5350	4.234
19. 2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-nitro)AI	5300	3.883
20. 2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3',4'-dinitro)AI	5320	4.597

I=Indole. B=Thionaphthene-indigo. T=Thionaphthene. AI=Acenaphthylene-indigo.

Considerable difficulty was experienced in reducing the dye, 2-(5 iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)acenaphthylene-indigo, to a vat and the vat remained faintly pink even after prolonged reductive treatment as in the case of other methoxy compounds³. The other dyes of the acenaphthenequinone series dissolve in alkaline hydrosulphite, producing either a yellow or a brownish yellow colour, and the original colour is imparted to cotton when exposed to air.

Guha⁴ supported the structure of Goldstein⁵ and observed that for methoxyacenaphthylene-indigos resistance to vatting was due to steric hindrance, the methoxy group shielding the 8'-carbonyl from the influence of external reducing agents.

Apart from the shielding effect, the strongly electron-repelling group-OMe, *ortho* to the carbonyl, is also likely to meet the electron-accession requirements of the carbonyl carbon internally, thus rendering it less ready to accept an electron from an external source, in the reduction process.

3. Guha and Sinha, *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 415; 1957, 34, 777.

4. *Ibid.*, 1952, 29, 787.

5. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 342.

TABLE II

Lyses.	Constituents & glacial acetic acid used.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour in conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton.	Found.	Reqd.
3-(5-Iodo)indole-2'-(5'-iodo)-B	5-Iodo-iasatin (0.193g) + C(0.106 g.) + 30 ml.	0.30 g.	314°	Yellowish green	Reddish violet	I: 24.1% S: 6.2	23.91% 6.02
3-(5-Iodo)indole-2'-(4'-chloro)-B	5-Iodo-iasatin (0.546 g.) + 4-chlorothioindoxyl (0.369 g.) + 40 ml.	0.70	208-90°	Yellowish green	Violet red	I: 28.7 Cl: 7.9	28.88 8.07
2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-8'-Al	Acenaphthenequinone (0.182 g.) + C(0.276 g.) + 25 ml.	0.40	> 303°	Green	Orange-red	I: 28.7 S: 7.2	28.86 7.27
2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)Al	3-Chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.54 g.) + C(0.69 g.) + 40 ml.	0.98	308-10° (shrinking from 307°)	Grass-green	Violet-red	I: 27.0 Cl: 7.6	26.7 7.5
2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)Al	3-Bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.457 g.) + C(0.483 g.) + 55 ml.	0.65	295-90°	Olive-green	Orange-red	Br+I: 40.1 S: 5.9	39.88 6.16
2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)Al	β -Methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0.424 g.) + C(0.552 g.) + 60 ml.	0.90	310°	Deep green	Faint pink	I: 27.2 S: 6.9	27.0 6.8
2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-8'-(3' or 4'-nitro)Al	3-Nitroacenaphthenequinone (0.227 g.) + C(0.270 g.) + 20 ml.	0.12	204-93°	Do	Brownish black	I: 26.3 S: 6.5	26.18 6.6
2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-8'-(3',4'-dinitro)Al	3,4-Dinitroacenaphthenequinone (0.272 g.) + C(0.276 g.) + 20 ml.	0.35	> 310°	Dirty brown	Blackish brown	I: 23.8 S: 6.9	23.06 6.03

Al = Acenaphthylene-indigo.

C = 5-Iodothioindoxyl.

B = Thionaphthene-indigo.

Alternatively, hydrogen bonding might also be involved, thereby reducing the probability of reduction⁶.

A small difference in absorption maxima has been observed when chlorine and bromine are substituted in the 3'-position of the acenaphthylene-indigos. Methoxy derivative shows greater shift towards the longer wave length, although the molecular weight is less than that of chloro and bromo dyes. The substitution of nitro group in the 3'-position of the acenaphthylene indigo produces a more pronounced bathochromic effect than the corresponding chloro and bromo substitution. The absorption maxima of the acenaphthylene-indigos have the sequence: 1'-methoxy > 3',4'-dinitro > 3'-or 4'-nitro > 3'-chloro, 3'-bromo > unsubstituted.

The above mentioned dyes, when arranged in order of intensities, have the order: 3',4'-dinitro > 3'-chloro > unsubstituted > 1'-methoxy > 3'-bromo > 3'-nitro.

It will be seen from Table I that the weighting of the dye molecule by substitution is not the only factor contributing to the bathochromic shift in the absorption maximum; the nature and characteristics of the substituent groups are also contributing factors.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo.—Acenaphthenequinone (0.182 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) and 5-iodothiaindoxyl (0.276 g.) was added to it. To the resulting red solution HCl (conc., 1.5 ml) was added and clusters of deep red needles separated immediately. The mixture was then boiled for 25 minutes, filtered hot, and washed with little acetic acid and hot water.

The indole-thionaphthene-indigos and acenaphthylene-indigos, described in Table II, were prepared in a similar way in presence of HCl (conc., 1.5-3.0 ml) and purified by recrystallisation from xylene.

These dyes are soluble in high boiling solvents, such as, pyridine, nitrobenzene, and aniline, and dissolve in H₂SO₄ (conc.) producing characteristically coloured solutions from which the original dyes are reprecipitated on dilution with water.

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